

Chemistry of bis-2' Cyanoethyl Derivatives of some Aromatic Amines: Part V*. Preparation of some new Tertiary Amino Benzaldehydes and a study of some of their Reactions

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4 NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino 2-ethoxy and 2 : 6-dimethylamino benzaldehydes have been prepared for the first time. Some of the reactions of these aldehydes and also of 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino 2-methoxy and 2-methyl benzaldehydes have been studied. *p*-N-methyl-N-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde which has so far been known through some of its derivatives has now been isolated in the pure form.

Braunholtz and Mann¹ have made an extensive study of the cyanoethylation of several aromatic primary amines. Their method has been extended to dicyanoethylation of *m*-5-xylylidine². Recently *m*-anisidine³ and *m*-phenetidine⁴ have been dicyanoethylated in this laboratory.

Similarity of the cyanoethyl derivatives to NN-dialkyl anilines led A. Thomas and Ittyerah⁵ to formylate NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl aniline and NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-toluidine. Singhal and Ittyerah³ have formylated NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-anisidine. Study of some reactions of *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde has been made by Asthana and Ittyerah⁶.

In the present communication the preparation of 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzaldehyde (I, R = H, R₁ = OC₂H₅) and 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2 : 6-dimethyl benzaldehyde (I, R = R₁ = CH₃) using dimethyl formamide and phosphorus oxychloride is described.

The aldehydes after purification were characterised by the preparation of suitable derivatives. The I.R. spectrum of the aldehyde (I) shows the characteristic aldehydic-CH

* Part IV. *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 741.

1. J. T. Braunholtz and F. G. Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3046.

2. P. I. Ittyerah and F. G. Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3179.

3. O. P. Singhal, Km. Veena Gupta and P. I. Ittyerah, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **29**, 69.

4. Veena Gupta and P. I. Ittyerah, Private communication.

5. A. Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah, *This Journal*, 1964, **38**, 41.

6. B. P. Asthana and P. I. Ittyerah, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 232.

stretching at 2841 and 2762 cm^{-1} ; aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1639 cm^{-1} ; $-\text{CN}$ band at 2203 cm^{-1} , and Ar-N at 1350 cm^{-1} .

The I.R. spectrum of 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino 2:6 dimethyl benzaldehyde also shows characteristic bands of the aldehydic- $\text{C}-\text{CH}$ at 2840 and 2710 cm^{-1} ; the CN band at 2217 cm^{-1} ; and Ar-N at 1348 cm^{-1} .

The formation of *p*-N-2'-cyanoethyl-N-methylamino benzaldehyde (II) has been reported by A. Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah. They could not obtain this in the pure form but some derivatives of this aldehyde in pure form have been prepared. Now the aldehyde has been obtained in pure crystalline form in 28.3% yield.

The I.R. spectrum of the aldehyde (II) shows aldehydic- CH stretching at 2849 and 2778 cm^{-1} ; $-\text{CN}$ band at 2222 cm^{-1} , phenyl ring breathing at 1587, 1541, 1517 cm^{-1} and C-Ar-N band at 1351 cm^{-1} .

During formylation it has been observed that the yields of the aldehydes are much higher if the dimethyl formamide-phosphorus oxychloride mixture is allowed to cool, and then the amine added slowly in small quantities with stirring. By this modification *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde (I, $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{H}$) and 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (I, $\text{R} = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$) have been obtained in 85.1 and 73.1% yield respectively as against 66.6 and 64% respectively, reported by A. Thomas and Ittyerah⁵.

The aldehydes (I, $\text{R} = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{OCH}_3$ or $-\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$) were condensed with compounds like malonic acid, diethyl malonate, 2:4 dinitro toluene and cyanoacetamide. Mild hydrolysis of diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene malonate (III, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$)

yielded a dicarboxylic acid (IV) while an attempt to prepare the tetra carboxylic acid (V) was not successful.

Treatment of the diethyl ester (III) with hydrazine hydrate yielded the cyclic amides (VI; R = CH₃, OCH₃ or OC₂H₅).

Several cyanine dyes have been prepared from the aldehydes and these will be reported later.

EXPERIMENTAL

Formylation of NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-m-phenetidine; formation of 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-amino-2-ethoxy-benzaldehyde.

To dimethyl formamide (5.84 g., 1.2 mol.) placed in a round bottomed flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and a reflux condenser was added with stirring, phosphorus oxychloride (3.1 g., 0.34 mol.) and the mixture was cooled to room temperature. NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-phenetidine (4.88 g., 0.34 mol.) was slowly added with stirring. After addition the contents were stirred and refluxed on a steam bath for 3 hr. The dark liquid was then cooled and poured over crushed ice. It was neutralized with crystalline sodium acetate, and the mixture left overnight when the aldehyde separated. It was collected, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The aldehyde (4.94 g., 75.8%) was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 147°. Found : N, 15.68; C₁₅H₁₇O₂N₃ requires N, 15.49%.

p-Nitro phenyl hydrazone of the aldehyde was prepared by refluxing equimolecular quantities of the aldehyde and para-nitro phenyl hydrazine in ethanol containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid for ten minutes. After cooling the red hydrozone which separated out was collected and recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 226°. Found : N, 20.42; C₂₁H₂₂N₆O₃ requires, N, 20.69%.

The 2 : 4 dinitro phenyl hydrazone of the aldehyde was obtained as deep red crystals, insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. It was purified by washing successively with hot ethanol and acetone; m.p. 246°. Found : N, 21.34; $C_{21}H_{21}N_7O_5$ requires N, 21.73%.

The semicarbazone of the aldehyde was prepared in the usual manner and after recrystallization from ethanol melted at 232°. Found : N, 25.42; $C_{16}H_{20}O_2N_6$ requires N, 25.61%.

The azine of the aldehyde was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde, hydrazine hydrate, ethanol and glacial acetic acid for thirty minutes. The azine which separated out as a yellow solid was purified by repeated washing with hot ethanol and acetone, m.p. 280°. Found : N, 20.62; $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_8$ requires, N, 20.81%.

Formylation of NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-m-5-xylylidine; formation of 4 NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl amino 2 : 6 dimethyl benzaldehyde

The method used was the same as described for 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzaldehyde mentioned earlier. The crude aldehyde was crystallised from large volume of ethanol and was obtained as pale yellow crystals. Found : N, 16.04; $C_{15}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 16.47%.

The 2 : 4 dinitro phenyl hydrazone of the aldehyde was prepared in the usual manner and purified by washing with hot ethanol and acetone, m.p. 276°. Found : N, 22.88, $C_{21}H_{21}O_4N_7$ requires N, 22.53%.

The azine of the aldehyde was prepared in the usual manner and was purified by repeated washing with boiling ethanol, m.p. 275°. Found : N, 22.46, $C_{30}H_{34}N_8$ requires N, 22.13%.

Purification of p-N-2'-cyanoethyl-N-methyl amino benzaldehyde

Formylation of N-2'-cyanoethyl-N-methyl aniline was carried out in the usual manner using phosphorus oxychloride and dimethyl formamide. The crude product was left in a well stoppered bottle for two months when the aldehyde separated as solid. Two crystallizations from aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) gave pale yellow needles of the aldehyde, m.p. 74°. Found : N, 14.93; $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.89%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl amino-2-methoxy cinnamic acid was obtained using the procedure recommended by Robinson and Shinoda⁷. The aldehyde (0.52 g.), malonic acid (0.22 g.), piperidine (3 drops) and pyridine (0.5 g.) were heated together on a steam bath for 10 hr. The golden yellow liquid thus obtained was extracted with sodium-bi-carbonate solution and the extract acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated acid was collected and purified by reprecipitation. The pale yellow crystals of the acid were obtained in 66.5% yield. m.p. 207°. Found : N, 14.32; $C_{16}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.05%.

Diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methoxy benzylidene malonate (III, R = OCH₃). The aldehyde (I, R = H, R₁ = OCH₃, 1.93 g.), diethyl malonate (1.6 g.) and piperidine (4 drops) were heated for 12 hr. in an oil bath at 105–110°. The golden yellow viscous liquid on treatment with ethanol (10 ml.) and with vigorous scratching with a glass rod gave lemon yellow crystals of the product. After recrystallisation from ethanol the ester melted at 118°. Yield, 52.2%. Found N, 11.40; C₂₁H₂₅O₄N₃ requires N, 10.96%.

Cyclic amide of diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methoxy benzylidene malonate. The ester (III, R = OCH₃, 0.6 g.), hydrazine hydrate (0.2 g., 90%) and aqueous ethanol (15 ml., 50%) were gently refluxed for an hour. The pale yellow solution obtained was kept overnight when the amide crystallised out. It was filtered and washed with hot ethanol. The yellow crystals of the cyclic amide melted at 272°. Yield : 78.5%. Found : N, 20.62; C₁₇H₁₇O₃N₅ requires N, 20.65%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methoxy benzylidene cyanacetamide. The aldehyde (I, R = H, R₁ = OCH₃, 0.52 g.), cyanacetamide (0.17 g.), absolute ethanol (15 ml.) and piperidine (2 drops) were mixed and refluxed for 2 hr. The yellow crystalline product which separated during heating were filtered and recrystallised from a large volume of ethanol, m.p. 248°, yield 91.2%. Found : N, 21.92; C₁₇H₁₈O₂N₅ requires, N, 21.61%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methoxy benzylidene 2 : 4 dinitrotoluene. A mixture of the aldehyde (0.26 g.), 2 : 4 dinitrotoluene (0.18 g.) and piperidine (1 drop) was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. The mass first melted to a clear liquid, but soon resolidified. The solid was digested with hot hexane to remove the gummy matter and then washed with a large volume of boiling ethanol and acetone. The product was obtained in deep purple crystals, m.p. 223°, yield 99.3%. Found : N, 17.11; C₂₁H₁₉O₅N₅ requires N, 16.62%.

The aldehyde (I, R = H, R₁ = OC₂H₅) was condensed with diethyl malonate, cyanacetamide, and 2 : 4 dinitro toluene. Attempts to condense the aldehyde with malonic acid was unsuccessful. The methods employed in all these condensations were the same as those described earlier. The following compounds were obtained.

Diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzylidene malonate. Yield 54.5%, m.p. 113°. Found : N, 10.58; C₂₂H₂₇O₅N₃ requires N, 10.16%.

Cyclic amide of diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzylidene malonate. Yield 58.5%, m.p. 281°. Found : N, 19.98; C₁₈H₁₉O₃N₅ requires N, 19.83%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzylidene cyanacetamide—yield 89.1%, m.p. 242°. Found : N, 20.54; C₁₈H₂₀O₂N₅ requires N, 20.71%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxy benzylidene 2 : 4 dinitro toluene—yield 93%, m.p. 193°. Found : N, 16.17; C₂₂H₂₁O₅N₅ requires, N, 16.09%.

The aldehyde (I, R = H, R₁ = CH₃) was condensed with diethyl malonate and hydrazine hydrate.

Diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene malonate—yield 52.2%; m.p. 118°. Found : N, 11.40; C₂₁H₂₅O₄N₃ requires N, 10.96%.

Cyclic amide of diethyl 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene malonate—yield, 59%; m.p. 250°. Found : N, 22.12; $C_{17}H_{17}O_2 N_5$ requires N, 21.66%.

4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene malonic acid. 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene diethyl malonate (0.5 g.), ethanol (5 ml.) together with saturated sodium-bi-carbonate solution (8 ml.) were taken in ar.b. flask and a vigorous stream of steam was blown through it for an hour. The pale yellow solution was filtered from suspended impurities, cooled, and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated product was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, yield, 71%; m.p. 178°. Found : N, 12.6; $C_{17}H_{17}O_4 N_3$ requires N, 12.84%.

Attempts to prepare a tetra carboxylic acid by the hydrolysis of 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzylidene diethyl malonate using alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave an intractable mass which could not be further purified.

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